

RESEARCH BRIEF

Designing a scalable multi-tracking network

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Abstract—This technical brief investigates a scalable multi-tracking network system that incorporates a number of sensors to actuate and interact with other networks. The network integrates all the information received from the changes tracked by the sensors and send them into a centralised monitoring system. The monitoring tracker is able to make choices that depend on the conditions of the environment and through a parametrised approach activate and trigger more mechanisms for further actions.

Index Terms—modeling, multi-tracking networks, scalability, methodology, distributed systems

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of technologies has enabled large-scale deployment of distributed devices able to monitor environmental, industrial, and infrastructural resources. Devices collect physical data, which are transmitted through communication networks to centralized platforms in which information is processed, visualized, and used for decision and action-making.

Low-power communication technologies play a critical role especially when provision of data at high speed rates is required in areas with limitations in power supply. Applications requiring long-range connectivity and low energy consumption have emerged recently as widely accepted solutions particularly in environmental monitoring and industrial automation.

II. EXISTING TECHNOLOGIES

Device-based monitoring systems are fundamental components in such network infrastructures. Distributed devices are able to monitor environmental characteristics through sensors sensitive in changes of temperature, humidity, and other physical quantities used for decision-making.

In Fig. 1 is shown a hybrid distributed - centralised system in which a control monitoring device is used to instruct, alter, control, start and pause on demand specific terminals depending on the needs of the contained environment [1, 4]. A wide range of devices can be integrated into monitoring platforms depending on the application requirements [2].

A multi-tracking system is a monitoring system, that can read from multiple sensors, record and act on predefined aims, using principles such as resistance, capacitance, inductance, voltage and others [4, 3]. A tracking board with sensors, including temperature, can measure the physical factors of its surrounding environment avoiding overheat or freezing that can reduce the operational function of another interconnected infrastructure.

As a rule of thumb, a sensor can be described by

$$y = f(x) \Leftrightarrow y = \sigma \cdot x + b \quad (1)$$

where x is the measured quantity, y the electrical produced signal and f is non-linear function. The function f describes the conversion from x to y . In many cases the relationship between x to y is simplified to a linear equation with a specific offset b .

Fig. 1. A multi-tracking system that consists of a control monitoring mainframe, a complex of sensor devices in real-time communication.

III. MODEL / FRAMEWORK

The processing of the data acquired from the sensors is dependent on the domain that is going to be incorporated. In some cases, in a case of fire, the temperature is a critical factor, while in case of erosion humidity is more important. To activate specific trigger points an actuator can be incorporated, an estimator, that will initiate an action to another complex of control systems. A decision making choice can be approached through the following actuator unit:

$$y(x|y_i) = \int \int f(x_i) dx_i dy_i \quad (2)$$

In Fig. 2 it is presented the integration of multiple units that can act as triggers for further actions to other systems. Having integrated data from multiples sensors, it is possible to increase the complexity, and at the same time the information for appropriate factual actions.

IV. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

Although an encrypted tunnel is an optional layer it is recommended to create virtual nets and add a network layer through use of VPN tunnels. This layer can improve the visibility of the network and therefore its protection position [3]. This way allows the integration of isolated zones, protecting

the propagation of a security flaw from one zone to another. The communication is over the same infrastructure but over a virtual network.

Fig. 2. A preliminary multi-sensor monitoring system with multiple data integrated from multiple sources connected through a gateway.

In the following setup the parameters of an Alfa AWUS036ACM communication device in monitor-mode are modified to connect to a VPN Proxy provider:

```
#!/usr/bin/bash

#PARAMETERS SETUP for
CHANNEL=5
BAND=bg #2.4GH, a=>5GHz
CARD_NAME=wlan0
if [[ ! -z $1 ]];then
    SSID=$1
fi

#Create Hotspot
nmcli dev wifi hotspot ifname $wCARD_NAME ssid "$SH_NAME"
    password "$SH_PASS" channel "$SH_CHANNEL" band "$SH_BAND"

# Set up NAT rules
#iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o eth0 -j MASQUERADE

#Connect the card to another network
nmcli device wifi connect "$SSID" ifname "$DEF_CARD-NAME"

#Set up routing, via 192.168.0.1 dev eth0
ip route add 192.168.1.0/24

#vpn connect
echo "CONNECT TO VPN"
piactl connect
```

V. EQUIPMENT AND DESIGN

In this section we are going to present a methodology of how to create a multi-tracking system that processes data from multiple sensor terminal devices, Fig. 1. For the configuration of the system an agora multi-moduled adapter on a single board was used. It includes the BME680 (high-accuracy gas, pressure, humidity and temperature), VL53L0X for laser-ranging, ICS-4342 (mic), the BEM 680, Si7021, ICM-20602 and LSM9DS1 with temperature, humid integrator, gyroscope, accelerometer, angular rate and magnetometer.

The Sangoma U100 USBfxo as two port foreign exchange office (FXO) for PSTN support, with other POTS in twisted-pair cables has also been used for emergency calls. Finally a TTN Network is able register devices and integrate data sent.

Open-loop and closed-loop mechanism has been incorporated to adjust continuously the monitoring of their environment, control and activate other devices.

VI. RESULTS AND CONSIDERATIONS

A scalable multi-tracking sensor network comprises of multi-tracking units that integrates information and actuate new action under specific conditions. A methodology was given by using an agora embedded board as a preliminary implementation. The provided hardware can be extended for further features and applications in interior multiple domains. Environment monitoring, farming, cargoes and transportation are some of its use.

One of the main concerns can be weak connectivity, insufficient protection mechanisms, fallacies into the hardware and infrastructure, and inaccessibility due to compromised setups. Compatibility, power critical applications, battery employment, costs, and increasing time delays due to wearing out of components need to be considered. Lastly, encryption techniques, compromisation methods, sustainability and role-based mechanisms will need to be considered.

VII. CONCLUSION

A multi-tracking network can be extended to a monitoring system, that can handle input from multiple nodes and incorporate mechanisms for more actions and control. The methodology presented provides a generalised approach in which isolated networks can be used to improve the capabilities of a network structure. All these are considered core components that enable a reliable connection between nodes, including optimisation and protection. In this way a centralised monitoring system can be constructed at a reliable and consistent manner.

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This work was part of a preliminary concept developed from a multiple case product. The work demonstrated the framework, concepts and methods used.

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